

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ADOPTED BY TEACHERS FOR QUALITY ASSURANCE IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ENUGU STATE

Prof. Loyce C. Onyali and Ugwu, Adaobi O.

Department of Educational Management and Policy, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

Email: lc.onyali@unizik.edu.ng, adaobiugwu49@gmail.com

Phone Number: +2348036772836, +2348063378780

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18455605>

Abstract: This study comparatively analyzed the classroom management practices adopted by teachers for quality assurance in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State. Two specific purposes, two research questions, and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 22,480 secondary school teachers in the 885 secondary schools comprising 299 public secondary schools and 586 private secondary schools in Enugu state. A total of 1,124 teachers made up of 367 public secondary school teachers and 757 private secondary school teachers from 45 schools in the study area, representing 5% of the population were sampled using multistage sampling procedure. A structured questionnaire, “Classroom Management Practices Adopted by Teachers for Quality Assurance Questionnaire (CMPATQA) was used for data collection. The instruments were face validated by three experts. Internal consistency coefficients of 0.81 and 0.80 was obtained for CMPATQA using Cronbach’s Alpha statistical method. The researchers administered the instrument to the respondents with the help of six research assistants. Data were analyzed using Mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that public secondary school teachers agreed on one of the two classroom management practices investigated (effective communication) while private secondary school teachers disagreed on the other classroom management practice (instructional monitoring). From the results of the hypotheses, significant difference was established in the adoption of effective communication while no significant difference was established in the other variable of the study. Based on the findings, the researchers recommend: more in-service training and workshops to strengthen the communication skills of public and private school teachers with less experience in areas of active listening, clarity of instruction and use of feedback to improve on their management practices for quality assurance; school principals should implement a structured monitoring system that regularly observe and assess teachers through classroom observation for improved classroom management that promotes quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Keywords: Classroom Management Practices, Effective Communication, Instructional Monitoring, Public Schools, Private Schools.

Introduction

Education is considered as the most essential instrument for preparing people for life and changing society to be relevant, adequate, and competitive in the global economy. It is the process of imparting knowledge, skills, technology, cogent ideas learned, either officially or in a relaxed way to improve the basis for human capacity development, both physically and mentally to fit into the society (Chukwu, 2023). The quality of education that a country provides to the citizens determines their level of contribution to national development. In Nigeria, the educational system is systematically structured into pre-primary, primary, secondary and tertiary education.

Secondary education which is the focus of the study is the third formal schooling system that provides a vital connection between elementary and tertiary education. It equips students for higher education or self-reliance. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), secondary education is the education given in an institution for children within the age range of 12 to 18 years plus. The goals of secondary education in Nigeria as spelt out by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) is that secondary education seeks to provide an increasing number of primary school pupils with opportunity for education of a higher quality, irrespective of sex or social, religious, and ethnic background, diversify its curriculum to cater for difference in talents, opportunities and roles possessed by or open to students after their secondary school course, equip students to live effectively in the modern age of science and technology, raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the dignity of labour and live as good citizens, inspire its students with a desire for achievement and self-improvement both at school and in late life.

In Nigeria, secondary schools are categorized as either public or private in Nigeria. Public secondary schools are referred to as educational institutions that are owned, financed, and controlled by the federal or state governments and they are day or boarding schools or both. Public schools are established to provide equal educational opportunities to the masses, regardless of their background, and they are typically funded by taxpayer's money, they are affordable but relatively less stable (Fakunmoju, 2023). According to Ugwu (2023), public secondary schools are post-primary institutions of learning established, controlled and financed by the government. On the other hand, private schools are owned, financed, and controlled by individuals, associations, or organizations, and are often established with the aim of educating students and making profit. It is also pertinent to mention that there are mission secondary schools which are owned by missionaries and partly controlled by the Government. Alafiatayo, Anyanwu, and Dauda (2019) highlighted that private secondary schools are owned by individuals, associations, or organizations, while public secondary schools are financed by the government to provide equal education opportunities to the masses irrespective of their background.

Private secondary schools are post-primary institution also known as non-governmental schools where individuals, group of persons, voluntary organizations or mission bodies establish and manage the affairs of the schools. This is in line with the view of Ogakwu (2013) that private schools are established and run by individuals, missions and

organizations with the approval of the government. The need for private secondary schools in Nigeria, according to Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD, 2017) came up because the cost of education is quite enormous which requires alternative mode of funding as government finds it difficult to bear alone hence require the attention and participation of other interested group of persons, organizations and individuals to render a helping hand in the provision of functional education to all citizens. This clarion call on individuals to help finance education has led to the proliferation of private secondary schools in Nigeria (Ejuchegahi, 2024).

Although similar curriculum is used in both public and private secondary schools, the key differences between public and private schools are in funding, class size, teacher-student ratio, and access to resources. Public schools receive funds from public taxes and government budgets while private schools are not supported by the government but instead they depend on private investments, endowments, tuition fees, and donations. This implies that tuition fees at private schools are usually more expensive than public schools. In relation to class size and teacher-student ratio, private schools usually offer more individualized attention and personalized classroom management because of their smaller class sizes and lower student-teacher ratio. Majority of the private secondary schools in Enugu State have limited number of students in the school and in the classrooms and most parents prefer to send their children to these private schools. In contrast, public schools in Enugu State often have larger class sizes as a result of increased enrollment, which may limit student-teacher interaction and make classroom management more difficult. Regarding access to resources, improved teaching aids such as technology and instructional materials seem to be given to teachers in private schools in Enugu state to aid their teaching process while public school teachers sometimes find it more challenging to utilize technology in their classrooms due to limited resources. This seems to be the reason why it is common to find many parents and guardians still prefer to send their children and wards to private secondary schools despite the fact that they are more expensive than public schools because they believe that there are better levels of academic planning in private school, with the private school owners upholding higher standards of education. However, teachers' job performance in relation to their management of classroom ensures adequate learning and credible outcomes that helps in the realization of educational goals and objectives.

Classroom management involves all the practices and methodologies that teachers apply to create a class environment that is conducive for teaching and learning activities (Hussain et al., 2022). Classroom management includes all the efforts teachers make in the following areas: organizing the students, coordinating the activities, monitoring their behaviors, ensuring effective learning process, providing instruction through interactive communication, getting feedback from learners, preparing and utilizing instructional materials. It entails facilitating learning, maintaining discipline among learners, evaluating learning outcome, ensuring that the problem of above average learners are being solved, relating one on one with learners, being mindful of their basic needs, providing basic information to learners, assisting learners in developing coping skills, providing an exemplary behaviour for learner as well as reinforce their performance through motivational techniques (Osakwe, 2014). In the view of Petrusheva and Popeska (2023), classroom management practices are applied by teachers in their everyday practice

to enable students effectively work and learn on a daily basis. The aspect of teachers' activities that could be used to evaluate their classroom management practices has been pointed out by researchers such as Sayson (2019) as effective communication, motivation, discipline, inclusion, , use of reward, teacher-student relationship, time management, diversity recognition, instructional monitoring. This is in line with the view of Asiyai (2011) who sees classroom management practices as the tactics employed by teachers for better teaching and learning in the classroom. These tactics according to Asiyai include: providing instruction through interactive communication, preparing and utilizing instructional materials in facilitating learning, maintaining discipline, giving clear and simple instructions, reinforcing their performance through motivational techniques among others. Having looked at the opinion of different authors about classroom management practices, the study mainly focused on effective communication and instructional monitoring practices. These two classroom management practices were chosen because they allow an in-depth analysis of their impact on learning outcomes, student engagement, and overall instructional effectiveness. This focused approach makes comparing how these practices vary between public and private secondary schools easier, offering valuable insights for quality assurance in education. In addition, both public and private schools deal with peculiar challenges in these areas.

Effective communication is connected to the practices that teachers adopt to promote comprehension and engagement in the classroom, ensuring that students understand expectations, instructions, and feedback. This practice helps to create an enabling educational environment that encourages collaborative thinking, minimizes misunderstanding, and improves the teaching and learning process. For better understanding of classroom instruction, there should be effective communication which entails the transfer of messages or information initiated by the teacher to the students either in the form of teaching, students' discussion and conversation (Okorji, 2014). Good communication in the classroom helps to make lesson clear and easy for students to learn, it serves as an important instrument for effective classroom management for the attainment of the school goals (Balci, 2011). There is a link between teaching and communication because teachers are constantly imparting new knowledge or transmitting information. This agrees with the thoughts of Sayeski and Brown (2014) that teachers can create highly engaging instruction by providing frequent opportunities for students to respond in the classroom. Effective communication in the classroom helps to make lessons clear and easy for students to learn by creating an atmosphere that is conducive for learning in the school. Communication of information observed during instructional monitoring and getting feedback from students is an important practice employed by teachers in the management of classrooms. This is because teachers' communication skill goes a long way in determining students' zeal to be learners, be interactive in class and enhance students' monitoring.

Instructional monitoring involves keeping track of students' learning by teachers for the purposes of making instructional decisions and providing feedback to students on their progress. Monitoring the students in the classroom is an important aspect of classroom management. According to (Prasad, 2008), instructional monitoring helps the school to keep a watchful eye on students' achievement and success. Pollock (2011) opined that monitoring the progress of the students in the classroom and giving them feedback is a skill that class teachers can acquire

through careful observation and having special interest in the students. Instructional monitoring helps the teacher to identify his strong and weak areas to help them strategize to boost and seek for quality processes for a positive output. (Baron, 2010). According to Ahmed and Pierre (2024) classroom management involves the supervision and monitoring of all the things that take place in the classroom. He went further to state that public and private schools share a similar vision of preparing learners to become self-reliant and contribute to national development, but they differ in several ways, including their method of instructional monitoring. Given the above situation, there is need for proper motivation of teachers to enable them actively deal with the problem of instructional monitoring and improper management of available classrooms in secondary schools for quality assurance in the system. Ultimately, teachers' adoption of this practice will provide students with necessary academic assistance, get them ready for success and strengthen the attainment of quality assurance in education.

Quality assurance involves all the processes that contribute to the success of the end-product (the learner) in terms of the learning outcome. Quality assurance is about continuous improvement in the teaching-learning process. Ayeni (2010) describes quality assurance in education as the systematic management, monitoring and evaluation of performance of school administrators, teachers and students against educational goals to ensure consistent documentation, review and decision towards quality improvement in institutional management, teaching and learning processes for the achievement of set standards in schools. Therefore, there is the need that all stakeholders in the implementation process must play appropriate roles to ensure that the end-products of the process will be geared towards realizing the expected quality encapsulated in the goals of education.

Quality assurance practices remain crucial in the management of schools to promote students' attitude towards academic activities and for the achievement of educational goal in general (Asuquo and Onyinye, 2022). All around the world, including in Nigeria, the creation and application of efficient quality assurance systems are essential to the success of secondary education. In the light of this, the Nigerian government has set quality criteria for secondary education with reference to internal quality assurance procedures. The Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2013) provided national education quality assurance handbook for basic and secondary education in Nigeria, the national standards for education quality are contained in this handbook. According to FME (2013), Quality standards are the goals to which all learners, teachers, staff and those who lead and manage schools should aspire to achieve. They are sometimes erroneously referred to as minimum standards but these are actually quality standards that focus on improving learning outcomes. Other quality assurance practices include: curriculum review and development, assessment and evaluation policies, learning resources and facilities, monitoring and feedback mechanism.

According to Atanda and Olaifa (2022), public and private secondary schools seem not to be providing quality education to the expected level because as important as education is to the citizens in Nigeria, it is still experiencing challenges that prevent equal access and quality assurance. Hence, the achievement of quality assurance in education will be greatly enhanced if teachers in Nigeria's public and private secondary schools, including those in Enugu State, utilize a variety of classroom management practices. However, the situation in some public and private secondary schools in Enugu State raise questions about whether or not teachers actually adopt classroom

management practices in their teaching in secondary schools in the state.

Statement of the Problem

Classroom management is the bedrock of teaching and learning in any country. Nigerian public and private school teachers need to be efficient in handling classroom management issues to produce quality students who will compete with their counterparts in other parts of the world as teachers are expected to be skilled communicators and instructional leaders. Despite the important role of teachers in classroom management at all levels of education, some public and private secondary school teachers in the area of study seem not to be utilizing effective classroom management practices which may negatively affect student learning outcomes in public and private schools, as it does not allow students active participation in the learning process and classroom activities. In turn, students' ability to gain quality knowledge is needed to meet set standards for quality assurance in education.

Considering that public secondary schools in the area of study appear to be dealing with classroom management issues of overcrowding and low student engagement which seems to be higher in public schools, the rate of instructional monitoring also seems inadequate. These issues may be affecting the quality of instruction and holistic educational experience of students in the state's public secondary schools, as seen by the increase in private secondary schools and the apparent preference of parents and guardians for private schools. However, public secondary school teachers in Enugu state are considered to be more skilled, competent, and efficient in terms of communication while private schools appear to excel in areas such as providing instructional support to students. On the other hand, the excessive focus of private schools on profit-making seem to hurt staff professional development, as the quality of teachers are questionable, with high rate of teacher stress and burnout which in turn affects the educational standards.

Hence, the attainment of quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu state is unlikely to occur if this trend is not rectified. In addition, there seems to be a paucity of empirical studies on the comparative analysis of classroom management practices adopted by teachers for quality assurance in public and private secondary schools in the area of study, hence the need for this study. The problem of the study is: Do public secondary schools adopt classroom management practices for quality assurance more effectively than their private school counterparts in Enugu state.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to comparatively analyze the classroom management practices adopted by teachers for quality assurance in public and private secondary schools in Enugu state. Specifically, the study compared the;

1. Effective Communication practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State for quality assurance.
2. Instructional Monitoring practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu state for quality assurance.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to provide answers for the study:

1. What are the effective communication practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State?
2. What are the instructional monitoring practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State on effective communication practices for quality assurance.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State on the instructional monitoring practices used for quality assurance.

Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study was conducted in Enugu State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 22,480 secondary school teachers (7,343 Public and 15, 137 private) in the 885 secondary schools comprising 299 public secondary schools and 586 private secondary schools in Enugu state. The sample size of the study was 1,124 teachers made up of 367 public secondary school teachers and 757 private secondary school teachers from 45 schools (5% of the population) drawn using multistage sampling technique. Structured questionnaires titled: “Classroom Management Practices adopted by Teachers for Quality Assurance Questionnaire (CMPATQAQ)” was used for data collection. The instruments were face validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Internal consistency co-efficient of 0.87 and 0.96 were obtained for CMPATQAQ using Cronbach’s Alpha statistical method. The researchers administered the instrument to the research participants with the help of six research assistants. Out of the 1,124 copies distributed, 1,087 copies from 351 public and 736 private secondary school teachers were returned duly completed, and used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The mean scores were used to interpret the data by categorizing the results into levels using Cohen (2013) range of values, thus: 1.00-1.50, very low extent; 1.51-2.50, low extent; 2.51-3.50 moderate extent; 3.51-4.50, high extent, and 4.51-5.00, very high extent. The t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was: a null hypothesis was not rejected where the calculated p-value was greater than the stipulated level of significance value (0.05). The reverse is the case where the calculated p-value was less than the stipulated level of significance. All analyses were carried out using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 25.

Results

Research Question One: What are the effective communication practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Effective Communication Practices Adopted By Teachers for in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Enugu State for Quality Assurance

	Public (n=351)	Private (n=736)
--	----------------	-----------------

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Paste the key classroom rules in an appropriate spot in the classroom.	2.94	.70	Agree	2.45	.53	Disagree
2.	Use non-verbal cues to show acceptance or disapproval such as facial expressions and gestures.	3.03	.67	Agree	2.56	.60	Agree
3.	Provide students with regular feedback on their performance and conduct	3.03	.71	Agree	2.49	.54	Disagree
4.	Engage students in continuous communication.	2.43	.76	Disagree	2.47	.54	Disagree
5.	Encourage teaching and learning in the classroom using questions and responses.	2.68	.61	Agree	2.43	.58	Disagree
6.	Give students precise instructions for every activity in the classroom so they'll constantly understand what to do.	3.16	.66	Agree	2.59	.63	Agree
7.	Provide clear directions for classroom activities so that the students will know what to do at any given time	3.01	.71	Agree	2.56	.62	Agree
8.	Teach students with a tone that won't intimidate them in the learning process	2.87	.66	Agree	2.53	.58	Agree
9.	Clearly explain to students the consequences of their behaviour in the classroom	2.94	.70	Agree	2.49	.56	Disagree
10.	Keep students engaged by identifying them by their names.	3.01	.69	Agree	2.56	.60	Agree
11.	Give each student several chances to contribute in class	3.09	.72	Agree	2.48	.54	Disagree
12.	Present lessons with accuracy and clarity for better understanding of the topics	2.89	.65	Agree	2.52	.56	Agree

Table 1 shows respondents' mean rating on effective communication practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State. The mean ratings for public secondary school teachers on all the 12 items ranged from 2.43 to 3.16 while that of private school teachers ranged from 2.45 to 2.59. This means that effective communication is better adopted in public secondary schools than private secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Question Two: What are the instructional monitoring practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Instructional Monitoring Practices Adopted By Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Enugu State for Quality Assurance

S/N	Items	Public (n=351)			Private (n=736)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
13.	Observe how well students follow the rules in the classroom	2.80	.66	Agree	2.81	.73	Agree
14.	Give students classwork after teaching a specific topic.	2.94	.72	Agree	2.99	.77	Agree
15.	Adjust the teaching strategies based on ongoing assessment of students' progress for continuous improvement	3.16	.66	Agree	3.22	.70	Agree
16.	Use questions to assess students' comprehension of the content being taught during class discussions.	3.01	.71	Agree	3.16	.76	Agree
17.	Correct students' assignments	2.87	.66	Agree	2.94	.73	Agree
18.	Grade the homework of the students	2.92	.69	Agree	2.91	.74	Agree
19.	Analyze students' achievement to aid in decision-making	3.06	.68	Agree	3.16	.67	Agree
20.	Mark students' notebooks	3.07	.73	Agree	3.06	.72	Agree
21.	Review knowledge of students periodically to ensure they comprehend learning contents.	2.91	.66	Agree	2.87	.68	Agree
22.	Encourage self-assessment among students to foster a sense of responsibility and ownership of their own learning	2.88	.71	Agree	2.71	.67	Agree
23.	Record completion of homework and award grades	3.17	.65	Agree	3.08	.63	Agree
24.	Caution students when they sleep in the classroom while teaching and learning is going on	2.89	.70	Agree	2.88	.73	Agree
25.	Encourage achievements of students in the classroom to promote acceptable behavior	3.20	.61	Agree	3.27	.58	Agree

Table 2 shows the mean ratings of respondents on the instructional monitoring practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State. The findings of the study showed that teachers from public and private secondary schools adopted all the instructional monitoring practices for quality assurance. This means that teachers from public and private secondary schools monitor their students well and the adoption of these instructional monitoring practices help them in setting clear learning objectives , assessing

students' progress, providing feedback, evaluating and improving the conditions and techniques of classroom instruction to ensure all students meet learning standards in the schools for quality assurance.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One; There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State on effective communication practices for quality assurance.

Table 3: t-test Summary of the Ratings of Public and Private Secondary School Teachers on Effective Communication Practices for Quality Assurance

Source of variation	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	P-value	Remark
Public	351	2.92	.25	1085	2.14	.03	Sig
Private	736	2.46	.31				

The analysis of the test of hypothesis one in Table 3 shows that the p-value (.000) is less than .05. However, the null hypothesis was not upheld. This signifies that there is significant difference between the mean ratings of teachers in public secondary schools and private secondary schools on effective communication practices for quality assurance in Enugu State with the mean score for public secondary school teachers (M=2.96, SD=.25) being significantly greater than that of those in private schools (M=2.46, SD=.31); $t(1085) = 2.14, p = .03$.

Hypothesis Two; There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State on the instructional monitoring practices used for quality assurance.

Table 4: t-test Summary of the Ratings of Public and Private Secondary School Teachers on the instructional monitoring Practices for Quality Assurance

Source of variation	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	P-value	Remark
Public	351	2.98	.24	1085	.87	.38	Not Sig
Private	736	3.00	.29				

The analysis of the test of hypothesis two in Table 4 show that the mean score for public secondary school teachers (M=2.98, SD=.24) is not significantly less than that of those in private schools (M=3.00, SD=.29); $t(1085) = .87, p = .38$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on the instructional monitoring practices used for quality assurance in Enugu State is not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Effective Communication Practices Adopted By Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools

Findings on the difference between the adoption of effective communication practices by teachers in public and private secondary schools as displayed in Table 1 revealed that effective communication is adopted at a high

extent in public secondary schools than private secondary schools in Enugu State. The findings in Table 3 also showed that there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of teachers in public secondary schools and private secondary schools on effective communication practices for quality assurance in Enugu State. The finding is in line with the findings of research conducted by Obiekwe and Uwaezuoke (2021) who reported that effective communication is vital for the maintenance of a school environment that is conducive for quality teaching and learning. This agrees with the findings on providing clear direction because teachers are meant to communicate the learning goals, instruction and procedure, expectations, feedback and encourage students to become confident and actively engage in the classroom. The findings on calling students by their name in the classroom agreed with Sayeski and Brown (2014) who found that teachers' creation of highly engaging instructions provides frequent opportunities for students to respond in the classroom. The finding is also in line with the findings of Tariq and Ullah (2024) who sees classroom communication as a vital tool used by teachers to ensure students' active participation in the classroom and this in turn impacts students' academic achievement. The findings of the present study on presenting lessons with accuracy and clarity is in line with the findings of Okorji and Unachukwu (2014) who found that effective communication practices in the classroom which entails the transfer of messages or information initiated by the teacher to the students either in the form of teaching, students' discussion and conversation leads to a better understanding of classroom instruction. The findings agreed with Fashiku (2017) who found that the maintenance of effective communication in the classroom by teachers is vital because communication as a process occupies a central position in the classroom daily interactions and learning only takes place when the students understand the message of the teacher through his teaching. Effective communication practices of the teachers are indispensable in ensuring quality assurance. Though there is need for engagement of students in continuous communication, in secondary schools, the finding showed that there is need for teachers in public and private secondary schools to improve on this area. They ought to continuously engage students in communication because when teachers adopt effective communication practices, lessons will be clear and easy for students to learn, an atmosphere that is conducive for learning will be created in the school and the quality of teaching and learning in schools will be enhanced.

Instructional Monitoring Practices Adopted By Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Enugu State for Quality Assurance.

The findings in Table 2 on the instructional monitoring practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance showed that instructional monitoring is adopted at a high extent in both public and private secondary schools in Enugu State. Similarly, the results in Table 4 indicated that there is no significant difference between the adoption of instructional monitoring practices by public and private secondary school teachers in Enugu State. The interpretation of the findings is that when teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State consistently adopt the practice of instructional monitoring in classroom management this will result to students meeting learning standards in the schools for the attainment of quality assurance. The finding supported Abbas et al. (2022) who found that teachers' utilization of instructional

monitoring as an internal micro-inspection process promotes regular resource utilization and propels impactful learning in the school for the attainment of an effective education system. The finding is in agreement with Ahmad (2011) who found that the teachers poses instructional monitoring necessary for improved learning. Monitoring the students in and out of the classroom by the teachers does not only enhance good behaviour among the students but also promotes students' academic performance. The finding agreed with Adeyemo (2012) who states that secondary school teachers have the ability to carry out instructional monitoring in creating a safe and effective learning environment for students' quality education in schools. The study findings also tallies with the findings of Dudek et al. (2018) with emphasis that monitoring of students through close observation helps to prevent misbehavior in the classroom and promotes students' academic achievement. The findings of the study is not in agreement with that of Nwankwo, Omebe and Anikeze (2019) that a low level of classroom instructional monitoring is being utilized by teachers as classroom management practices in public schools. Leveraging instructional monitoring is an effective way of managing the classroom to promote quality assurance in secondary schools. Teachers therefore should maintain their adoption of instructional monitoring of student activities in the classroom for quality assurance. Regarding the difference between the extent of adoption of instructional monitoring practices for quality assurance in public and private secondary schools, the results as displayed in Table 4 indicated that there is no significant difference between the extent of adoption of instructional monitoring practices by teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State. This signifies that teachers proper monitoring of students by the teachers leads to improvement in the conditions and techniques of classroom instruction and management.

In line with the above finding, Adeleke, Bambi and Frank (2022) study that investigated the relationship between instructional supervisory practices and teaching effectiveness in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, showed among others that effective instructional supervisory practices such as classroom observation and ensuring well implemented curriculum enhances teachers' effectiveness in the classroom. Also, the study established that there is a positive relationship between supervision of curriculum implementation, classroom management and teaching effectiveness.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was found that there is a difference in the extent of adoption of effective communication practices between public and private secondary school teachers for quality assurance as public secondary school teachers adopted effective communication practices more than private secondary school teachers in Enugu State. However, both public and private secondary school teachers adopted instructional monitoring practices. , the study concluded that the adoption of classroom management practices by public and private secondary school teachers is a valuable practice for promoting quality assurance in secondary schools in Enugu State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Ministry of Education should conduct regular in-service training and workshops that concentrate on strengthening improving teachers' communication skills in areas of active listening, clarity of instruction and use of feedback for the promotion of quality teaching and learning in schools.
2. Principals should implement a structured monitoring system for regular observation and assessment of teachers through classroom observation and use of feedback mechanism to reinforce quality learning.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, A.H., Umar, .T. Yusuf, .S. Hamza, .A. and Nafisa, .A.A. (2022). Instructional Supervision and Teacher Effectiveness in Senior Secondary Schools in Tambuwal Local Government Area, Sokoto State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in STEM Education*, 4(2), 58–74. <https://doi.org/10.31098/ijrse.v4i2.1171>.
- Adeyemo, B. (2012). Classroom management practices in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis, Department of Educational foundation, University of Port Hacourt.
- Ahmad M. (2011). Application of classroom management strategies in public and private sector at school level in Pakistan. *Journal of manager science*. 4(1):55-66.
- Ahmed, N., and Pierre, du P. (2024). The Role of Classroom Management in Enhancing Learners' Academic Performance: Teachers' Experiences. *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, 5(1), 202–218. <https://doi.org/10.46627/silet.v5i1.364>.
- Alafiatayo, Bunmi, M., Anyanwu, R.I. And Dauda, Nana O. (2019) Relative Analysis of Public and Private Senior Secondary Schools Students' Achievement in Biology in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *ATBU, Journal of Science, Technology & Education* 7(1), 239-246
- Asiyai, R.I. (2011). Effective Classroom Management techniques for secondary schools. *International Multi-Disciplinary Journal, Ethiopia*. 5 (1), 18-25.
- Asuquo, M. E. and Onyinye, C. (2022). Internal School Quality Assurance Practices and Undergraduate Students' Attitude towards Academic Activities: A Case of Public Universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Education Studies*, 15(4), 108. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v15n4p108>
- Atanda, O. and Olaifa, S. A. (2022). Comparative Study of Quality Assurance Practices in Unity Schools and Private Secondary Schools in Kwara And Oyo States, Nigeria. *Daengku: Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Innovation*, 2(1), 19–27. <https://doi.org/10.35877/454ri.daengku680>

- Ayeni, A.J. (2010). Teachers' instructional task performance and principals supervisory roles as correlates of quality assurance in secondary schools in Ondo State. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation. Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.
- Balci, E. (2011). The roles of teachers, Education sociology, (Editor M. Aydın). Ankara. TDFO Bilgisayar-Press.
- Branon, T.S. (2010). The effects of classroom beliefs/dialogues on student academic success. Dissertation completed at California State University
- Chukwu, C.C. (2023). Education No Longer at Ease: The Necessity to Build a New Employable and Productive Society for Nigerian Youths through Quality Education. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 9(6), 7–27. <https://doi.org/10.56201/ijee.v9.no6.2023.pg7.27>
- Cohen, J. (2013). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. Cambridge: Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203771587>
- Dudek, C. M., Reddy, L. A., and Lekwa, A. (2018). Measuring Teacher Practices to Inform Student Achievement in High Poverty Schools: a Predictive Validity Study. *Contemporary School Psychology*, 23(3), 290–303. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40688-018-0196-8>
- Ejuchegahi, A. A. (2024). An Analytical Study of the Proliferation of Private Schools in Nigeria. *Traektoriâ Nauki*, 10(1), 6007–6014. <https://doi.org/10.22178/pos.100-17>
- Fashiku, C.O. (2017). Effective Communication: Any Role in Classroom Teaching – Learning Process in Nigerian Schools. *Bulgarian Journal of Science and Education Policy*, 11(1), 171–187.
- Fakunmoju, S. B. (2023). Self-reported Symptoms of Anxiety in a Sample of Public versus Private Secondary School Students in a District in Southwest Nigeria. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 42, 209–230. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v42i1.8622>
- FME (2010). Quality assurance instrument for basic and secondary education in Nigeria. Revised edition. Federal inspectorate service.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National Policy on Education. Lagos NERDC Press.
- Hussain, I., Saifi, I. L., Farooqi, A.H., Khakwani, S., and Parveen, A. (2022). Classroom management practices and students' performance: A causal perspective of secondary level students. *Journal of Social Sciences Advancement*, 3(3), 110–116. <https://doi.org/10.52223/jssa22-030302-38>.

- Nwankwo, I., Omebe, M. and Anikeze, C. (2019). Extent of Teachers' Classroom Management Practices for Quality Teaching and Learning in Secondary Schools in Ebonyi State. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.30845/ijhss.v9n1p12> on (12/08/2025)
- Obiekwe, K. and Uwaezuoke, M.I. (2021). Interpersonal and communication skills used by teachers to achieve quality classroom management in secondary schools in Imo State. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation* 2(5) 106-112
- OECD. (2017). The Funding of School Education. In *OECD Reviews of School Resources*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264276147-en>
- Ogakwu, V.N. (2013). Comparative Study of management practices between public and private secondary schools. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Okorji, P.N. and Unachukwu, G. (2014). *Communication in school organization: A skill Building Approach*. Nimo: Rex Charles and Patrick Publishers.
- Osakwe, R.N. (2014). Classroom management: A tool for achieving quality secondary education in Nigeria. *International Journal of education* 6(2): 1948-5476.
- Petrusheva, K.M. and Popeska, B. (2023). Classroom Management Practices: Methods and Approaches Applied for the Purpose of Student's Personal Development. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 6(12). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v6-i12-81>
- Pollock, J.K. (2011). *Making effective use of classroom management techniques*. Ibadan. University Press.
- Prasad, R.D. (2008). *The school, teacher-student relationships and values*. New Delhi. India. APH Publishing Corporation.
- Sayeski, K. L., and Brown, M. R. (2014). Developing a Classroom Management Plan Using a Tiered Approach. *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 47(2), 119–127. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0040059914553208>
- Sayson, E. (2019). Preferred Classroom Management Techniques of Senior High School Teachers of the University of San Agustin A.Y. 2018-2019. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21904.46082>
- Tariq, M. and Ullah, H. (2024). Impact of Teachers' Communication Skills on Academic Achievement of Students at Secondary School Level. *Journal of Higher Education and Development Studies (JHEDS)*, 4(1), 104–117. <https://doi.org/10.59219/jheds.04.01.49>